

RI-VIS - Summary report and roadmap for future activities

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Executive Summary

Over the past 12 months, RI-VIS organised three international Research Infrastructure (RI) symposia with colleagues in different world regions: Africa, Latin America and Australia. These symposia were co-organised with local organising committees, and held over 2-3 days in February, June and October 2021, respectively. In addition, together with the CREMLINplus project, a one-day Europe-Russian Federation symposium on RIs was organised in December 2021.

Initially planned as in-person events, the symposia were organised as virtual symposia, due to the ongoing Covid-19 pandemic and related travel restrictions. The attendees had various opportunities to interact with the speakers, panellists and other attendees from the different regions and fields of sciences and to exchange ideas, to network and discuss potentially new collaborations. The speakers and attendees represented RIs, science policy organisations and research institutions from Europe and the other world regions, and were drawn together by a common interest in RIs and international RI cooperation.

Prior to the symposia, RI-VIS produced three white papers, which provide recommendations on how to increase collaboration between European RIs and counterparts from Africa, Latin America and Australia. The papers collate the insights of a total of 21 experts from RIs, policy-makers and relevant governmental institutions from the three regions collected through in-depth interviews. Furthermore, RI-VIS drafted guidelines for the effective communication in Africa and Latin America.

The symposia were useful in bringing together relevant stakeholders and provide a forum to discuss new or strengthen existing partnerships as well as common challenges and opportunities. The organisers of these international symposia gained valuable experience, in particular with the various formats (e.g., panel discussions, sessions with oral presentations, keynote lectures, thematic satellite workshops, networking sessions) and virtual tools (e.g., Wonder app, Whova platform) to encourage the attendees to actively contribute to the discussions and to stimulate the communication and networking among the attendees before, during and after the symposium. These lessons will be valuable for the organisation of future RI symposia. In fact, the responses of the attendees to our post-symposium survey confirmed that there is a strong interest to organise similar symposia in the future. Future events would help to follow up on the discussions of the RI-VIS meetings in 2021 and to continue the efforts to bring the RIs from different world regions closer together.

This summary report and roadmap for future activities will describe the main take-home messages of the RI-VIS symposia and outline recommendations for future activities. Several case studies are described in this deliverable to illustrate in more detail how RI-VIS contributed to advance the collaboration between individual European RIs and their RI counterparts in other regions.

Detailed report on the deliverable

Background/Introduction

The mission of RI-VIS [1] is to 'Expand research infrastructure visibility to strengthen strategic partnerships.' The RI-VIS consortium consists of 13 partners representing 12 Research Infrastructures

(RIs) in various scientific fields, including biomedical sciences, social sciences and environmental sciences. Advisors from physics and an e-infrastructure (eRI) complement this group to ensure that RI-VIS represents RIs from across the scientific spectrum.

One of the objectives of the RI-VIS project is to create an outreach programme to provide information, bring RIs together with new target communities in other world regions and facilitate collaborative engagement.

RI-VIS (WP3) organised three international RI symposia with colleagues in Africa, Latin America and Australia. These symposia were held over 2-3 days, starting with the Africa-Europe Symposium on February 1-2, 2021, followed by the Latin America-Europe Symposium on June 15-17, 2021 (organised in collaboration with the EU-LAC ResInfra project [2]) and the Australia-Europe Symposium on October 5-7, 2021. Each symposium is described in detail in the RI-VIS deliverables D3.1-3.3, which are publicly available. In addition, together with the CREMLINplus project [3], a one-day Europe-Russian Federation symposium on RIs was organised on December 7, 2021 [4].

The aim of these symposia was to raise awareness of individual RIs, to identify measures to mitigate current challenges of international cooperation between RIs, to initiate new and strengthening existing collaborations, and to initiate networks in a sustainable way so that all stakeholders benefit. Due to the ongoing COVID-19 pandemic and travel restrictions, the symposia were organized as digital events.

Description of work

Organisational aspects of the international RI symposia

Many RIs have established, or started discussions about establishing new, collaborations with partners outside of Europe, either on a bilateral basis or as partners in larger, international consortia. The international cooperation between RIs is motivated by the ambition to (i) harness collective global knowledge and experience, (ii) support leveraging of new international funding for RIs, (iii) promote access to and exchanges between RIs, (iv) facilitate the mobility of researchers, (v) assist in meeting global challenges, or (vi) compensate each other's shortcomings with regard to available infrastructures [5].

Advancing these partnerships and initiating new collaborations critically depends on the relationships between people. Therefore, the RI-VIS symposia strive to bring like-minded people together, who share an interest in research infrastructures and international partnerships, and to create a platform for them to network and exchange ideas to facilitate cooperation across different world regions.

In Europe, the new ESFRI Roadmap 2021 includes 41 implemented European RIs and 22 RI preparatory phase Projects in the fields of energy, environment, health and food, physical sciences and engineering, social and cultural sciences as well as e-infrastructures. The **scope** of the RI-VIS symposia was deliberately broad to cover all scientific fields and to be as inclusive as possible. The speakers and panellists were selected to represent the perspectives of RIs from a **variety of scientific areas**. At the first two symposia, the sessions featured a mix of RIs from various scientific disciplines, whereas at the Australia-Europe symposia, different themes were defined for each day, for example, 'Health/Cancer' or 'Environment challenges/Climate Change'.

All RI-VIS symposia were initially planned as in-person events in the target region, to approach relevant RIs and researchers close to their home institutions. Unfortunately, the ongoing COVID-19 pandemic and related travel restrictions made the organisation of larger in-person symposia impossible, so **virtual symposia** were organised instead. There are several advantages of virtual events, and from an organiser's perspective, the ease by which participants and speakers are able to join these meetings and the considerably lower cost, in addition to environmental considerations due to a substantially reduced carbon footprint, are arguably the most important. Due to these considerations, and as virtual conferencing tools are now widely used, it is expected that virtual events will continue to replace (or complement) many in-person meetings in the future. Discussions between partners from different world regions via videoconferences, without the need to travel, has become more convenient and common practice, and will facilitate close collaborations and joint research activities despite the geographical distance.

The symposia were announced on the RI-VIS website with a large banner on the landing page. The **website** informed about the date of the event, the agenda (also available as a downloadable pdf-file), list of speakers with their affiliation details, organising committee, links to the respective white paper, registration details and contact details of the organisers, in case of questions.

The RI-VIS symposia were organised as one-time events, as opposed to, for example, established recurring (annual or biennial) meetings of scientific societies, so it was important to raise awareness about the symposia among the target audience. Research infrastructures, both internal and external to the RI-VIS consortium, announced the symposia via their own websites and newsletters as well as on the RI-VIS website. Social media posts, e.g., on Twitter, complemented these outreach channels. In addition, **promotion videos** were produced for the Latin America and Australia symposia, which are available on YouTube (for example, [Australia - Europe Symposium on Research Infrastructures](#)):

Considering the aim of the symposia, which is to bring people together to network and exchange ideas, the organisers put great effort into selecting formats and virtual tools that facilitate the active participation and interaction among attendees.

The event website provides all relevant information about the event, however it is static and limited in its ability to facilitate the interaction and lively communication between the attendees. Therefore, a commercial **online platform** (<https://whova.com/>) was set-up to create an interactive online environment for the participants. The online platform was available before, during and after the events, and provided the symposium participants and speakers with various means to engage with other attendees: by adding information to their profiles such as their affiliation, job titles and additional professional data; by directly approaching and contacting other attendees via in-app messaging; by inviting other attendees to meet-ups and virtual meets; by initiating discussions around a certain topic by adding a topic or social group in the community area of the platform; by uploading outreach material, e.g., handouts, flyers, and brochures to be shared with colleagues in the handout area; and by contacting and submitting questions and suggestions to the organisers. The participants could join the presentations either via live stream through the online platform or via a link to the videoconferencing app. The participants could submit questions either via the chat or Q&A function of the online platform and the videoconferencing app.

In our experience, when compared with similar virtual events that relied solely on an online videoconferencing or webinar tool, the online platform indeed simulated the attendee engagement and many discussions among attendees took place in parallel to and after the sessions of the main programme. After the symposium, the attendees were asked to rate the online platform, and the large majority (94%) of responded 'very good' and 'excellent'.

Arguably the most difficult aspect to replicate in a virtual format is the **networking**, which often takes place outside of the sessions of the main programme during coffee breaks, poster sessions, or social dinners. Allocating attendees randomly to smaller break-out rooms is a recurring theme at virtual events, but it is often disliked by attendees, who cannot choose their conversation partners. In our experience, virtual networking needs other formats. During all three symposia, an online tool Wonder [6], which facilitates a more authentic way of networking, where attendees can decide freely who they wish to talk to, was deployed. After joining the virtual networking session, attendees, who could be identified by their avatars, move around to look for other attendees they want to speak to. A virtual videoconferencing bubble automatically opens to start the conversation. More attendees can join the conversation, and participants can leave at any time and initiate another discussion. Confidential discussions about new project ideas can take place undisturbed by other attendees, when the

conversation partners lock their bubble. The organisers can proactively stimulate the discussion among like-minded attendees, who share an interest in a common topic, by setting-up virtual ‘areas’ around different themes. A list of participants, who are present at the networking session, is available, which allows the networking participants to easily locate individual attendees, who they wish to approach, and to invite them to join a specific conversation.

In our experience, networking attendees felt more comfortable to network in this setting, which is supported by a bespoke online networking tool. However, only a small group of attendees joined these networking sessions, which may be due to the challenge of working across diverse time zones (especially during the Australia-Europe Symposium on RIs) and/or the participants’ limited experience with the networking format. Based on the responses of the participants to the post-event survey, the majority of attendees (70%) rated the networking opportunities as 'very valuable' and 'extremely valuable'.

Note: The group picture of the RI-VS Latin America-Europe Symposium on RIs was shared on Twitter with the consent of the attendees featured.

The Africa-Europe and Australia-Europe symposia were originally planned to be held in countries, where the official language is English and the majority of speakers and participants were native or proficient English speakers. The majority of the speakers and attendees of the Latin America-Europe Symposium, however, are native Spanish speakers, with the exception of those from Brazil. In order to mitigate this potential language barrier and to ensure lively discussions during the meeting, the

organisers decided to offer **simultaneous interpretation** from English to Spanish and vice-versa by three native-speaking experts, so that the attendees, speakers and panellists could communicate in the language they felt most comfortable to speak. The translation was integrated into the videoconferencing solution, so that the interpreters provided their own audio channels for the language they are translating to (English and Spanish) and attendees could select the audio channel to hear the translated audio in their language of choice, as well as the option to mute the original audio instead of hearing it in a lower volume with their chosen language. This feature was very helpful to enable lively discussions among the attendees throughout the sessions, as many speakers and panellists (and probably many attendees) used the simultaneous interpretation. In our experience, simultaneous translation should be considered for similar meetings, where the majority of speakers and participants are not native speakers of the official language of the event.

Individual RIs, global RIs, multi-RI cluster projects, RI training initiatives or individual scientists can present their work as part of a **virtual exhibition**. At a virtual booth, interested attendees can learn more about RIs, watch videos, download handouts and other marketing content, or experience live showcases. Exhibiting RIs can inform about their access models, service offers, example projects and other relevant aspects, and engage directly with other attendees via chat. The time and investment needed for exhibiting RIs to set-up a virtual booth is considerably low in comparison with exhibiting at in-person events, where the exhibitors need to prepare and ship (or carry) plenty of booth material, including desk standees, chairs, backdrop, roll-ups, brochures, marketing material and give-aways. The virtual exhibition complemented the talks of the main programme and provided an opportunity for RIs to present themselves and raise awareness among the attendees. A similar number of virtual booths were set-up at the three RI-VIS symposia: 15 at the Africa-Europe symposium, 14 at the Latin America-Europe symposium, and 19 at the Australia-Europe symposium.

In comparison with booths at in-person events, however, the exhibitors can directly approach interested participants while they are visiting the booth, whereas this personal contact is lost in the virtual format, limiting the reach and impact for exhibitors. The limited visibility and opportunity to get in contact with many participants will most likely make virtual exhibitions less attractive for potential sponsors, which usually expect a return on their investment by being able to reach out to many event participants (the organisers of the RI-VIS symposia, however, did not approach any sponsors and offered virtual exhibitions for free).

In-person meetings can ideally be combined with visits of local institutes, facilities and infrastructures, which are organised in conjunction to the main event. These **site visits** offer the attendees unique insights into the infrastructure and state-of-the-art equipment of the platforms, and allow them to have a realistic behind-the-scene glance at where and how new discoveries are made. Considering that all RI-VIS symposia were held online, it was a challenge to organise such site visits of a local infrastructure virtually. The Latin America-Europe Symposium was originally planned as an in-person meeting at the Center for Research in Energy and Materials (CNPEM) in Campinas, Sao Paulo state in Brazil, which houses four world-class laboratories, which are open to the scientific community: the Synchrotron Light National Laboratory (LNLS); the Biosciences National Laboratory (LNBio); the Biorenewables National Laboratory (LNBR) and the Nanotechnology National Laboratory (LNNano). Dr. Ana Zeri, Coordinator of the beamline MANACÁ (MAcromolecular micro and NAnoCrystAllography), and Dr. Florian Meneau, Coordinator of the beamline CATERETÊ (Coherent And TimE RESolved ScATTering) kindly organised a 'Sirius virtual visit – a live tour through one of the most advanced synchrotron light sources in the world'. The attendees had the chance to virtually visit the CATERETÊ beamline, which provides unique capabilities in biological and soft materials imaging and dynamics experiments with a particular focus on the application of coherent X-ray scattering and diffraction techniques, and MANACÁ, which will be the first macromolecular crystallography beamline of Sirius and optimized for micrometric and sub-micrometric focus. The visit was a unique experience for the attendees and helpful to convey a better understanding of the operation of this infrastructure.

The scope of each symposium was broad and all scientific fields were covered. In addition to these thematically diverse sessions, several RIs organized **thematically focussed satellite workshops** in conjunction with the main symposia. Some of these workshops were well attended with over 100 participants from 20 countries. The workshops were organised by the individual RIs, together with their RI counterparts in the target region. Though the organisation of the workshops takes time and effort, they allow individual RIs to invite stakeholders from both regions and to organise a series of presentations and panel discussions around a particular scientific area, and offered the opportunity to reconnect with policy makers, researchers and infrastructure managers for future collaborations.

The symposia were organised in collaboration with **local co-organisers**. The Africa-Europe symposium was co-organised by Prof. Trevor Sewell at the University of Cape Town. The Latin America-Europe

symposium was co-organised with the EU-LAC ResInfra project, which brings together 18 partners from 14 Latin American and European countries, represented in the organising committee by Inmaculada Figueroa (EU-LAC ResInfra Coordinator), Sabina Guaylupo (EU-LAC ResInfra Project Manager), and Claudia Romano (Ministerio de Educación y Cultura Uruguay). The Australia-Europe symposium had the largest local organising committee, with delegates from many Australian RIs: Carina Kemp (Australia's Academic and Research Network, and chair of the local organising committee), Frankie Stevens (Australia's Academic and Research Network), Susie Robinson (Australian Plant Phenomics Facility), Wojtek Goscinski (National Imaging Facility), Stuart Newman (Therapeutic Innovation Australia), Luc Betbeder-Matibet (University of New South Wales), Julie Rothacker (Monash University), Michael Dobbie (Phenomics Australia), Merran Smith (Population Health Research Network), Tim Rawlings (Auscope), Michelle Heupel (Integrated Marine Observing System), and Jo Curkpatrick (Australian Plant Phenomics Facility). The organisers are grateful to the local co-organisers who were critical to the success of the symposia. Local organisers assisted by reaching out to speakers and panellists, raising awareness among the scientific community and ensuring that the symposia equally represent scientists and RIs from both regions (i.e., Europe and the target region), in addition to assisting in the organisational aspects, which required a significant commitment and time investment by the organising committee members.

The virtual meetings were well attended with 474 registrations for the Africa-Europe symposium, 614 registrations for the Latin America-Europe symposium, and 212 registrations for the Australia-Europe symposium. The organisers aimed for a **geographical balance** of the audience between attendees from the target region and Europe. While the proportion of African researchers at the Africa-Europe symposium was low (22% from Africa and 73% from Europe), the audiences of the second and third RI-VIS symposia were more geographically balanced, with 58% of the attendees of the Latin America-Europe symposium based in Latin American countries (35% in Europe) and 44% of the registered participants of the Australia-Europe symposium from 44% Australia (51% from Europe).

Before each symposium, RI-VIS (WP2) contacted 21 experts from RIs and policymakers from the respective regions, who are experts in the field of RIs and their funding/policy ecosystems in the different regions. Their insights have been collated in **three white papers** for Africa [7], Latin America [8] and Australia [5], which present examples of successful collaboration, lessons learned and possible challenges/bottlenecks. The white papers put forward numerous actionable region-specific recommendations for RI representatives as well as for policy makers and funders on how to increase collaboration between European RIs and counterparts. The white papers were shared with the participants via the online symposium platform and served as a teaser or further reading before, during or after the symposium.

Case studies:

RI-VIS, and in particular the symposia, which were organised in 2021, kick-start awards, the three white papers and the communication guidelines contributed to bringing RIs and researchers from various world regions together. They created further momentum surrounding the discussions about possible collaborations. In the following section, a few case studies are presented to illustrate these points.

Instruct-ERIC

Instruct-ERIC is the European research infrastructure for integrated structural biology. Instruct-ERIC offers access to high-end structural biology equipment and expertise through Centres of excellence in Europe in the areas of sample preparation, bimolecular analysis and 3D structural analysis. Instruct services include research visits or remote access to structural biology facilities, training courses, internships, computational tools and R&D awards.

In 2016, Instruct-ERIC solidified a collaboration with the University of Cape Town in South Africa. In conjunction with the first RI-VIS symposium, Instruct-ERIC and START (Synchrotron Technologies for African Research and Technology [9]) co-organised the virtual thematic workshop ‘Furthering Structural Biology in Africa’ [10], which aimed to further the relationship between Instruct-ERIC and structural biologists and other life scientists in South Africa. At the end of this workshop, Instruct-ERIC has signed a Memorandum of Understanding (MoU) [11] with the University of Cape Town, providing access to technology and staff for structural biology projects, as well as training opportunities and presence at networking events to further establish the partnership throughout the region.

Besides the collaboration with Africa, Instruct-ERIC has been building on long-standing collaborations with colleagues at CeBEM (Centre for structural biology of the Mercosur, [12]) in Latin America, supported by the projects RI-VIS, EU-LAC ResInfra and Microbes. CeBEM is the leading structural biology research infrastructure in Latin America with nine groups across Brazil, Argentina, Uruguay, Paraguay, and Venezuela. Activities and momentum surrounding the Latin America Symposium and satellite played an important part in strengthening these collaborative activities. Instruct-ERIC has since signed two new MoU with Latin American institutions [13]: the University of San Martin (UNSAM), and the School of Sciences, University of Buenos Aires (UBA), both in Argentina. Instruct-ERIC is now actively looking into funding opportunities for regional hub infrastructure in Latin America together with the Institut Pasteur Montevideo and Euro-BioImaging.

The institutions in South Africa and Argentina, with newly signed MOUs, and those international institutions which had previously signed MOUs with Instruct-ERIC were invited to participate in the Instruct-ERIC second international access call <https://instruct-eric.org/second-international-call>.

Euro-BioImaging ERIC and Global-BioImaging

Euro-BioImaging ERIC [14] is an established pan-European Research Infrastructure, established as a legal entity in 2019, after more than 10 years of preparation and comprising 137 imaging facilities across Europe, which offer open access services to the global scientific community. Latin America Bioimaging [15] is a network initiated in 2020 that brings together researchers, service providers, educators and commercial technology integrators in bioimaging in South and Central America.

Euro-BioImaging and Latin America Bioimaging share the same principles and have a commonality of intents, aiming at democratizing access to bioimaging technologies and at promoting advancements in biological and biomedical imaging. They are both partners of the Global BioImaging network [16], via which collaborate on many topics including exchange of best practices, training and capacity building. Via these interactions, they have jointly identified that similarities between the two regions exist and the lessons learnt in Europe may represent a tremendous insight for Latin America.

The RI-VIS satellite event entitled “Latin America Bioimaging Network: facts, experiences and challenges”, held on June 18th, 2021 was a key moment of exchange between the two partners. It allowed Latin America Bioimaging and Euro-BioImaging to strengthen the dialogue between the European and Latin American bioimaging communities, to involve the political actors involved in

building Research Infrastructures in both regions and to raise the visibility of the bilateral efforts made to build stronger interactions and common research activities.

Euro-Biolmaging is now actively looking into funding opportunities for regional hub infrastructure in Latin America together with the Institut Pasteur Montevideo and Instruct-ERIC.

EMBRC ERIC

The European Marine Biological Resource Centre (EMBRC) is a European research infrastructure that provides researchers and companies with access to marine organisms and the facilities to study them, including experimental facilities and technological platforms. EMBRC successfully applied for the RI-VIS Kick-start award, focussing on the isolation and characterisation of specific bioactives from a number of priority samples from the Institute for Microbial Biotechnology and Metagenomics (IMBM, [17]) at the University of the Western Cape in South Africa. This project is a very important opportunity for EMBRC to valorise its bioprospecting capabilities, which is one of the RI's strategic priorities. It is also an opportunity to establish a relationship between the IMBM (South Africa) and the EMBRC. For IMBM, this project offers an opportunity to explore and test the EMBRC capabilities to assess if it meets their needs in bioprospecting. If successful as a demonstrator, this project will build the foundation for a continuing collaboration. With reference to South Africa's unique biodiversity and IMBM's microbial collections and expertise, the project can position the participants for future collaboration in larger inter-continental (early) product development opportunities. It may also provide an opportunity to provide training and skills development to both the IMBM and the EMBRC.

EMRBC also started conversations with the South African Environment Observation Network (SAEON, [18]), the Integrated Marine Observation Network (IMOS, [19]) in Australia, and is in discussions with the University of Western Cape in South Africa to support their bioprospecting research. For the first two, conversations concern EMBRC's new European Marine Omics Biodiversity Observation Network (EMO BON, <https://www.embrc.eu/emo-bon>) project, shared protocols, standards, and data standards. For the University of the Western Cape it would be for providing services, with the ambition to set up a service level agreement in the future.

BBMRI

BBMRI-ERIC is a European research infrastructure for biobanking and biomolecular resources, which brings together all the main players from the biobanking field – researchers, biobankers, industry, and patients – to boost biomedical research. To that end, BBMRI-ERIC offers quality management services, support with ethical, legal and societal issues, and a number of online tools and software solutions. Ultimately, our goal is to make new treatments possible and enable precision medicine to the fullest.

Our first contact with the Latin American community was during the organization of a workshop for the project ADOPT BBMRI-ERIC - implementAtion anD Operation of the gateway for health into BBMRI-ERIC [20], in which we shared our expertise and helped to create a framework for international research infrastructures in the life sciences field. As part of our efforts to support biobanking in different regions of the world, we organised a biobanking workshop in Rio de Janeiro in early 2019. Focussing on biological resource infrastructures and building on existing initiatives and networks, the aim of the workshop was to help create similar infrastructures in Latin America and to facilitate cooperation with their European counterparts.

During the Latin America-Europe symposium, BBMRI-ERIC organized a satellite meeting together with the European, Middle Eastern & African Society for Biopreservation and Biobanking (ESBB), the topics of which included the clinical need for biobanking, ethical concepts and patient involvement, quality management systems, data collection management, and security. BBMRI-ERIC Director General Jens Habermann gave the audience an introduction to BBMRI-ERIC and the President of ESBB Rosita Kammler introduced ESBB. Then teams from both organizations instructed the participants on “How to build a biobank” and “Pre-analytics and Quality”, with time for questions and answers. The 30 participants of the workshop were highly engaged and interested in learning from our experiences.

EU-OPENSSCREEN

EU-OPENSSCREEN ERIC is the European RI for chemical biology and early drug discovery. The major approach to identifying novel chemical probes (which are useful tools to study basic biological processes) and novel drug leads (which can be further progressed into drug candidates and ultimately medicines) is the screening of large, diverse compound collections. This drug discovery process, however, requires (access to) a dedicated research infrastructure with high-throughput screening platforms, bespoke comprehensive screening compound collections, automated compound management capabilities and expertise. EU-OPENSSCREEN offers researchers worldwide access to such a critical infrastructure to support drug discovery efforts in academic and industry.

An important aspect in drug discovery is the quality of the screening compound collection. Indeed, pharmaceutical companies have made significant investments in the past decades to improve their own compound collections. Most academic compound collections mainly comprise compounds that are commercially available, but proprietary compounds synthesized by academic chemists as well as natural products represent a rich, untapped source for novel chemical diversity. In order to make these invaluable resources accessible, EU-OPENSSCREEN offers chemists the opportunity to make their compounds available, in a regulated and transparent framework, to a wider community of biologists, who screen these compounds in suitable bioassays. By doing so, chemists can expose their compounds to a broad range of different biological/drug targets to screen for unknown bioactivities of their compounds, which would otherwise not be feasible in individual one-to-one-collaborations. Once a compound has been identified as an active ‘hit’ compound, a research collaboration between the chemist (who submitted the compound) and the biologist (who developed the bioassay) can be initiated.

The three RI-VIS symposia represented a unique opportunity to raise awareness among the chemistry community in Africa, Latin America and Australia about this compound submission model. Over the past months, EU-OPENSSCREEN discussed in more detail with partners (supported by RI-VIS as one of four RI-VIS Kick-Start Awards) at Griffith University, Compounds Australia, Therapeutic Innovation Australia and Monash University in Australia the general requirements for the compound submissions, e.g., screening data deposition into EU-OPENSSCREEN’s public European Chemical Biology Database (ECBD, [21]), the mandate to disclose compound structures, the purity of compounds (>90%), the minimum amount of material as well as the logistics of the physical transfer of the material. These discussions are ongoing and will be continued beyond the lifetime of RI-VIS.

Besides the discussions in Australia, EU-OPENSSCREEN was approached, after the RI-VIS Africa symposium, by a chemist from the University of the Free State in South Africa, who was interested in the compound submission model. After several virtual follow-up meeting between the chemist and staff members of the EU-OPENSSCREEN Central Compound Management Facility (CCMF), a Material Transfer Agreement (MTA) was signed and the first African compounds will be submitted shortly.

Furthermore, discussions took place after the Latin American RI-VIS symposium with researchers in Costa Rica to share compounds. Besides synthetic compounds, the discussions are now revolving around the submission of natural compounds, which needs to be compliant to the '*Nagoya Protocol on Access to Genetic Resources and the Fair and Equitable Sharing of Benefits Arising from Their Utilization.*'

In addition to compound submissions, EU-OPENSREEN submitted a joint proposal, together with partners in South Africa, to organize a comprehensive one-week workshop on pre-clinical drug discovery in Cape Town with participants and instructors from various sub-Saharan countries. Furthermore, joint research proposals with scientists in Morocco and South Africa, respectively, have been submitted in response to national (German) funding calls, which are currently under review.

In short, RI-VIS contributed to and supported discussions between EU-OPENSREEN and various scientific partners in the three world regions to initiate and advance bi-regional cooperation on different areas, including the exchange of compounds, joint research proposals and local practical workshops.

Lessons learnt and recommendations

The format of the international outreach and partnering events is crucial. Virtual events, which aim to raise awareness and inform participants about individual RIs or initiatives, often deploy standard videoconferencing solutions and their agenda often predominantly consists of presentations, occasionally combined with a panel discussion. In order to facilitate a stronger engagement of the participants and emphasize the networking aspect of the event, additional interactive formats and bespoke software tools are necessary.

Networking is among the main reasons to attend scientific meetings and workshops. Unfortunately, networking at virtual meetings is often disappointing and inefficient, and most attendees do not participate in the virtual networking sessions at all. At the RI-VIS symposia, a dedicated online tool, which facilitated a more authentic way of networking, where attendees can decide freely who they wish to talk to, was deployed. Those participants that attended these networking sessions found that the networking format was 'very' or 'extremely valuable', but in-person meetings are clearly more conducive to create relationships than virtual meetings.

If meetings are held in countries, where the official language is not English or where the majority of speakers and attendees are not native English speakers, the language barrier may have a negative impact on how comfortable the participants feel to communicate with other participants or to contribute to open discussions. Therefore, simultaneous translation should be considered, so that the attendees and presenters can communicate in the language they feel most comfortable to speak and attendees can select the audio channel to hear the translated audio in their language of choice.

Site visits of local RIs and facilities, which are organised in conjunction to the main event, are a great experience to provide the participants with direct insight into the operation of the infrastructure. However, organising these site visits as part of a virtual event is a challenge and not always possible to integrate into the agenda of a virtual meeting.

Take home messages:

Enhancing the visibility of RIs is very important, and most European RIs are not well known outside of Europe. The symposia represented valuable platforms for discussions among European RIs and their counterparts in other world regions. They were important to make RIs known beyond the respective regions and led to a better understanding of the RI landscapes, existing RI initiatives and current RI-related needs. There is an interest worldwide in developing RIs locally and in collaborating with European RIs. Therefore, communication about the aims of any one RI, its service offer and how to engage with the RI remain an area to be improved.

The scientific community needs meetings like the RI-VIS symposia, as a forum for discussions about partnerships, resources and synergies so that more can be achieved together. As one survey respondent puts it: "Everyone - countries, governments, research bodies, groups and individuals - can benefit from interactions, exchange of ideas and proposals for collaborations."

The attendees agreed that global challenges require openness and international collaboration, and there was a strong interest to strengthen the collaborations and joint RI endeavours. The attendees concurred that RIs need international collaboration to ensure the best use of limited resources. Experts, who were also consulted for the White Papers, agreed that biregional collaborations will increase in the future.

The people at the RIs are the glue that builds collaboration, and these collaborations form best from individual relationships and connections. Small grants and other funding opportunities for bilateral collaborative research projects, practical workshops, and staff exchanges are important.

During the discussion, many challenges in all operational aspects of RIs are shared between RIs from the different regions, e.g., sustainable funding, maintaining human capital, managing data and demonstrating impact. Also questions like how to ensure the recognition of the role of RIs by researchers is common among RIs worldwide. In this context, RIs can learn from each other, and there is an interest to exchange experience how these challenges can be best addressed. Future meetings that cover these topics are needed to facilitate the continuation of these discussions in more detail.

In Europe, many established ERICs are set-up under the legal framework of a European Research Infrastructure Consortium (ERIC). The members of an ERIC are Member States, associated countries, third countries other than associated countries and intergovernmental organisations. It became clear from the discussions, that there is a strong interest for collaborations between RIs from different regions, but it is essential to have a legal framework that allows for the inclusion of non-European RIs to carry out collaborative projects together.

Conclusion/Next steps

Overall, the RI-VIS symposia were very successful and 1,300 participants registered for the three events. Based on the responses of the post-symposium surveys, the participants were very satisfied with the events and 94% confirmed that the sessions met their expectations. 92% of the attendees said that the events were 'very well' or 'extremely well' organized.

There is a strong interest in future follow-up meetings. 100% of the survey respondents said that they would recommend these symposia to others, and 94% confirmed that they are interested in a follow-up symposium in the future. The symposia were originally planned as in-person events, but needed to be held as virtual symposia due to the ongoing Covid-19 pandemic. As in-person meetings are more conducive to create relationships than virtual meetings, it is recommended that these follow-up

meetings are organized as in-person symposia to better reach out to the local scientific community in the target region and to allow for the organization of accompanying local site visits. The three symposia organized by RI-VIS focused on three world regions, i.e., Africa, Latin America and Australia, and similar outreach and partnering events should be organized in other regions like Asia and Northern America.

As described in the White paper on Recommendations towards cooperation between Australian and European research infrastructures: *'Many experts emphasized the importance of personal relationships in terms of sparking scientific or organizational collaboration between Australia and Europe. People getting to know one another through conferences, workshops, committees, and exchanges can lead to successful joint projects down the line.'* The use cases presented in this report illustrate how projects like RI-VIS contribute to bringing RIs and researchers from various world regions together and to creating momentum surrounding the discussions about possible collaborations. A follow-up project is therefore very desirable to continue the discussions, which have been initiated during the RI-VIS symposia, and to support the international cooperation between RIs from different world regions.

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